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GREB1, a molecule that functions like an estrogen receptor co-activator in breast cancer, is activated during lymph node metastasis in humans with small cell and non-small cell lung cancer.

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We previously identified GREB1 as a likely mediator of transformation in hormone-dependent tissues by functioning as a co-receptor with ESR1. Here we identify GREB1 activation in the lungs in humans with small cell and non-small cell lung cancer. GREB1 activation occurred during metastasis to the lymph nodes. GREB1 has functions in cancer, early at the single cell transformation stage, and late in disease during dissemination of the tumor to a secondary lymphoid organ (the lymph nodes).